

RECONSTITUTION OF THE CELESTIAL SPHERE:
SUGGESTIONS FOR A NUMERICAL STUDY OF ERROR PROPAGATION

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1. Introduction

The reconstitution of the celestial sphere consists in combining measurements of angles between stars in order to obtain the astrometric parameters of the stars, i.e. their positions, proper motions, and parallaxes. In addition to these unknowns the problem involves the determination of a number of "instrumental" parameters (or functions), which affect the angle measurements and must be calibrated mainly from the star observations themselves. These include the basic angle, the scale of the field of view (or rather the grid step), the tilt and orientation of the grid, and the motion of the nominal spin (z) axis on the sky. Although these are in reality continuous functions of time, they must for the solution be represented by a finite set of discrete numbers, e.g. by use of discontinuous step functions or series expansions. Only a certain subset of instrumental parameters is in general needed for describing the status of the instrument at a given instant.

The astrometric and instrumental parameters are in principle determined through a least-squares solution. Two approaches have been discussed; they may be referred to as the "direct" and "indirect" approaches.

The direct approach is to write down for each angle measurement the complete observation equation, involving as unknowns the ten astrometric parameters of the two stars observed, and the pertinent set of instrumental parameters. Although conceptually simple and straightforward, the approach may lead to severe numerical and data-handling problems when applied to the full-scale reconstitution problem, because of the size and special structure of the resulting normal equations.

The indirect approach allows a decomposition of the reconstitution by taking advantage of that the sky is scanned nearly along great circles, and that the star positions are constant during the few hours it takes to complete a great-circle scan (for the extreme case of Barnard's star the proper motion is about 0".003 per scan). Thus, we can first establish and solve (by least-squares or filtering) a set of observation equations for one or a few scans, the unknowns

being the relative star abscissas (star positions projected onto a reference great circle approximately coinciding with the scans, and referred to an arbitrary origin) and the relevant instrumental parameters. The resulting star abscissas from this scan and from all other scans are together taken as the input ("observed" quantities) of a least-squares solution for the astrometric parameters of the stars. All instrumental parameters are thus eliminated in the processing of individual scans (Step 1). The solution for the astrometric parameters comprises Step 2 and 3 in the three-step procedure.

There appears to be some advantages of the indirect approach. Firstly, it has already been demonstrated that it allows a decomposition (not necessarily the best one, however) which reduces the reconstitution problem to the solution of a system of equations not larger than about 1000 (viz. the astrometric parameters of a set of origin stars), indicating that the reconstitution is indeed numerically feasible. Secondly, the processing of individual scans in Step 1, especially by means of the filtering algorithm, allows a continuous monitoring of instrument and spacecraft behaviour and the incorporation of a detailed dynamical model of attitude motion (permitting "dynamical smoothing"), as well as a substantial reduction of the amount of data for further processing.

However, the direct approach is no doubt the more stringent, and therefore probably more accurate, if the practical difficulties can be overcome. Some of the advantages of the filtering could easily be incorporated in the direct approach, e.g. by letting the filter provide estimates of the individual angle measurements, which are the input for the direct solution, rather than of star abscissas. The practical feasibility of a direct solution remains however to be demonstrated.

The purpose of the present note is to describe formally the error propagation through the second half of the indirect solution, i.e. Step 2 and 3, in order to examine the rigidity of the reconstituted sphere, as obtained with different schemes of decomposition. The rigidity is quantitatively defined as follows.

Recall that, during the Phase A Study, the final mean error σ of an astrometric parameter was estimated by means of the formula

$$\sigma = \epsilon \cdot c, \quad (1)$$

where ϵ is the mean error per scan, i.e. the mean error of relative abscissas as obtained in Step 1, and c is the coefficient of improvement, representing the effects of combining, in the third step, all the absolute abscissa measurements on a particular star.

The absolute abscissas are obtained by adding to the relative abscissas a zero-point correction, unique for each scan and obtained in Step 2. (Alternatively, in a later scheme, the absolute abscissa of one star per scan, the "origin star" is obtained from its astrometric parameters, solved for in Step 2, and from this the zero-point correction.) In this process there is necessarily a degradation of accuracy depending on the non-rigidity of the reconstitution. To include that effect, Eq. (1) must be modified to

$$\sigma = \epsilon \cdot c / r, \quad (2)$$

where r is a dimensionless number between 0 and 1, measuring the rigidity of the reconstitution.

The rigidity r may be estimated for different decomposition methods by means of small-scale solutions, involving only a few hundred stars at most. It is envisaged that r increases monotonically as more stars and more observations are added, so that such a solution will at least provide a lower limit for the rigidity. It may even be possible to extrapolate the rigidity to the size of the full-scale reconstitution by asymptotic fitting.

2. Definitions

Notations and definitions in this note are more or less consistent with those of my earlier notes (76-10-19, 77-02-12, and 78-10-09), but for convenience they are all repeated here.

The stars are numbered $i = 1, 2, \dots, I$. Each star is characterized by its a priori mean position (λ_i, β_i) , and five astrometric parameters

$$\begin{aligned} a(i, 1) &\equiv \Delta\lambda_i \cos \beta_i && \text{(the correction to the longitude times } \cos \beta_i) \\ a(i, 2) &\equiv \Delta\beta_i && \text{(the correction to latitude)} \\ a(i, 3) &\equiv \mu_{\lambda_i} \cos \beta_i && \text{(the proper motion in longitude)} \\ a(i, 4) &\equiv \mu_{\beta_i} && \text{(the proper motion in latitude)} \\ a(i, 5) &\equiv \tilde{\omega}_i && \text{(the parallax).} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

At time τ (in years from the mid-epoch of observations) the true ecliptical coordinates of star i are

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda_i(\tau) &= \lambda_i + \Delta\lambda_i + \mu_{\lambda_i} \cdot \tau - \tilde{\omega}_i \cdot \sin[\lambda_i - \lambda_0(\tau)] / \cos \beta_i, \\ \beta_i(\tau) &= \beta_i + \Delta\beta_i + \mu_{\beta_i} \cdot \tau - \tilde{\omega}_i \cdot \cos[\lambda_i - \lambda_0(\tau)] \cdot \sin \beta_i, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\lambda_0(\tau) = \lambda_0(0) + 2\pi\tau$ is the longitude of the sun.

The scans are numbered $j = 1, 2, \dots, J$. One scan (j) contains the angle measurements obtained along a reference great circle (rgc) at a certain epoch $\tau(j)$. The finite duration of the scan is neglected, i.e. $\lambda_z(\tau)$ and $\beta_z(\tau)$ are assumed to be constant during the scan. The pole of the rgc for scan j is at $\{\lambda_r(j), \beta_r(j)\}$; the scan is counter-clockwise as seen from this point. Note that several different scans may be referred to the same rgc, e.g. because the same scanning pattern is repeated each year.

The observations are numbered $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$. It is convenient to define observations in such a way that they can be regarded as independent piece of information. However, the relative abscissa corrections derived in Step 1, being arbitrarily referred to the abscissa of an origin star, or to the average of abscissa corrections, cannot be expected to be uncorrelated, since they have a common zero-point error. If the covariance of the relative abscissas is known, it is possible to transform them to an equivalent set of uncorrelated quantities, or the covariance of the resulting astrometric parameters could be expressed in terms of the abscissa covariance. Since the typical form of this covariance is not known at present, I propose that, for the time being, it is assumed to be the same as if the relative abscissas were obtained as the differences between a set of fictitious "absolute" abscissa corrections, which are independent and of equal precision. With this hypothesis, the natural choice is of course to regard these absolute abscissas as "observations".

Observation k is thus the fictitious measurement of the absolute abscissa correction $\Delta\alpha(k)$, whereas the actually observed quantity is the relative abscissa correction

$$d(k) = \Delta\alpha(k) - \Delta\alpha(k_0), \quad (5)$$

where k_0 is the observation of the origin star on the same scan as k .

The relations between stars, scans, and observations are defined by the following functions. $i(k)$ denotes the star observed in observation k ; $j(k)$ is the scan to which observation k belongs; $k(i, j)$ is the observation of star i in scan j (if such an observation exists). The origin star of scan j is denoted $i_0(j)$; the observation of it in the same scan is $k_0(j) \equiv k(i_0(j), j)$. $L(j)$ is the number of relative abscissa measurements in scan j ; consequently, $L(j) + 1$ is the number of absolute observations (and the number of observed stars) in scan j .

It is furthermore assumed that the $K = J + \sum_j L(j)$ observations are chronologically ordered, i.e. that the first $L(1)+1$ observations belong to scan 1, starting with $k_0(1) = 1$; the next $L(2)+1$ observations belong to scan 2, starting with $k_0(2) = L(1)+2$, etc.

Let D be the $(K|1)$ array of absolute observations. According to our hypothesis its covariance is

$$C_D = E(DD^*) = e^2 I, \quad (6)$$

where e is the mean error of an absolute observation and I is the identity matrix of dimension $(K|K)$. [The expectation operator E in (6) and the following should actually be interpreted as $E(ab) - E(a)E(b)$.] The $(K-J|1)$ array d of relative abscissas is obtained by the transformation

$$d = RD, \quad (7)$$

where R of dimension $(K-J|K)$ is block-diagonal, $R = \text{diag}(R_1, R_2, \dots, R_J)$. The j :th block of dimension $(L(j)|L(j)+1)$ is

$$R_j = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & -1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & -1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & -1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (8)$$

The covariance of d is therefore

$$C_d = E(dd^*) = E(RDD^*R^*) = RE(DD^*)R^* = e^2 RR^*. \quad (9)$$

The $(K-J|K-J)$ matrix RR^* is also block-diagonal, the j :th block of dimension $(L(j)|L(j))$ being

$$(RR^*)_j = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ 1 & 2 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

We also define an array A of dimension $(5I|1)$ containing the astrometric parameters:

$$a(i, m) = A_{5i-5+m}, \quad m = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \quad (11)$$

and a matrix P of dimension $(K|5I)$ with elements:

6.

$$P_{k, 5i-5+m} = 0 \quad \text{if } i(k) \neq i, m = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5; \text{ otherwise:}$$

$$P_{k, 5i-4} = - [\sin \beta_r(j) - \sin \delta \sin \beta_i] / (\cos^2 \delta \cos \beta_i),$$

$$P_{k, 5i-3} = - \cos \beta_r(j) \sin[\lambda_i - \lambda_r(j)] / \cos^2 \delta,$$

$$P_{k, 5i-2} = \tau(j) \cdot P_{k, 5i-4}, \quad (12)$$

$$P_{k, 5i-1} = \tau(j) \cdot P_{k, 5i-3},$$

$$P_{k, 5i} = - \sin[\lambda_i - \lambda_o\{\tau(j)\}] \cdot P_{k, 5i-4} - \sin \beta_i \cos[\lambda_i - \lambda_o\{\tau(j)\}] \cdot P_{k, 5i-3},$$

$$\text{where } j = j(k) \text{ and } \sin \delta = \sin \beta_r(j) \sin \beta_i + \cos \beta_r(j) \cos \beta_i \cos[\lambda_i - \lambda_r(j)].$$

Thus PA is the $(K|1)$ array containing the absolute abscissa changes that results from the astrometric parameters in A.

Since the observations are ordered according to scans, it is possible to partition P into a column of submatrices P_j of dimension $(L(j)+1|5I)$.

3. Formal expressions for different solutions

3.1. Reference solution

Thanks to our definition of absolute abscissa measurements, we can immediately write down the fictitious observation equations corresponding to Eq. (1), i.e. the error estimates in the Phase A Study. They are

$$PA = D, \quad (13)$$

from which the least-squares solution is

$$A^{(1)} = (P^*P)^{-1} P^*D. \quad (14)$$

The subscript (1) signifies "solution no. 1". By means of Eq. (6), we find the covariance of this solution to be

$$C_A^{(1)} = E[A^{(1)}A^{(1)*}] = E[(P^*P)^{-1}P^*DD^*P(P^*P)^{-1}] = e^2 (P^*P)^{-1}. \quad (15)$$

Comparison with Eq. (1) shows that we should interpret e as the mean error per scan (ϵ), and the square-root of the diagonal elements of $(P^*P)^{-1}$ as the improvement factors c of Step 3. The computation of c is extremely easy since P^*P is block-diagonal, with one $(5|5)$ block per star. The solutions for the different stars are thus completely separated; the solution obviously

represents a perfectly rigid reconstitution of the celestial sphere ($r = 1$). Hence the name "Reference solution".

For other solutions, $s = 2, 3, \dots$, the overall rigidity is defined by

$$r^{(s)} = \left[\frac{\sum_l [C_A^{(1)}]_{ll}}{\sum_l [C_A^{(s)}]_{ll}} \right]^{1/2}, \quad (16)$$

with summation over all the diagonal elements of the two covariance matrices, $l = 1, 2, \dots, 5I$. Since the rigidity may well be different for the different kinds of astrometric parameters, we may also compute one rigidity measure $r_m^{(s)}$ for each kind of parameter ($m = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$), by restricting the summations in (16) to $l = m, m+5, m+10, \dots, m+5I-5$.

3.2. Solution using origin stars, correlations neglected

Since only relative abscissas $d = RD$ are in fact observed, the actual observation equation must be written

$$RPA = RD. \quad (17)$$

These equations are in fact correlated, as expressed in Eq. (9), but we may nevertheless perform a least-squares solution, although the result will not be optimal. The normal equations

$$(P^* R^* RP) A = P^* R^* RD \quad (18)$$

are however singular, since the origin of coordinates has not been fixed. This is resolved by appending six linear constraints on the astrometric parameters:

$$SA = 0. \quad (19)$$

Here, 0 is a $(6|1)$ array of zeroes and S is a $(6|5I)$ matrix, consisting of a row of I submatrices S_i of dimension $(6|5)$:

$$S_i = \begin{pmatrix} \sin \beta_i \cos \lambda_i & -\sin \lambda_i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \sin \beta_i \sin \lambda_i & \cos \lambda_i & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ \cos \beta_i & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sin \beta_i \cos \lambda_i & -\sin \lambda_i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \sin \beta_i \sin \lambda_i & \cos \lambda_i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \cos \beta_i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

Introducing a (5|1) array of Lagrangean multipliers, L , we obtain the non-singular system

$$\begin{pmatrix} P^* R^* R P & S^* \\ S & \emptyset \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} A \\ L \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P^* R^* R D \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (21)$$

where $\emptyset$ is a (6|6) matrix of zeroes.

Let $T^{(2)}$ be the upper-left (5I|5I) part of the inverse of the (5I+6|5I+6) normal equation matrix in (21). The solution for A in (21) is then

$$A^{(2)} = T^{(2)} P^* R^* R D. \quad (22)$$

The covariance of this solution is obviously

$$C_A^{(2)} = e^2 T^{(2)} P^* R^* R R^* R P T^{(2)}. \quad (23)$$

We shall aim at limiting the size of the largest matrices necessary to compute in full to dimension (5I+6|5I+6). This is possible by making use of the simple structure of R and the partitioning of P in submatrices P_j . Both $R^* R$ and $R^* R R^* R$ are of course block-diagonal; the j :th block, which is of dimension (L(j)+1|L(j)+1) is, respectively,

$$(R^* R)_j = \begin{pmatrix} L(j) & -1 & -1 & \dots & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

$$(R^* R R^* R)_j = \begin{pmatrix} L(j)[L(j)+1] & -L(j)-1 & -L(j)-1 & \dots & -L(j)-1 \\ -L(j)-1 & 2 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ -L(j)-1 & 1 & 2 & \dots & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -L(j)-1 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (25)$$

Eq. (23) can then be written

$$C_A^{(2)} = e^2 T^{(2)} \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^J P_j^* (R^* R R^* R)_j P_j \right\} T^{(2)}. \quad (26)$$

3.3. Solution using origin stars and taking correlations into account ("Rigorous solution")

The correlations among the observation equations (17) may be removed by transforming to

$$\text{HRPA} = \text{HRD} \quad (27)$$

by means of a $(K-J|K-J)$ matrix H satisfying

$$\text{HRR}^* \text{H}^* = I, \text{ or } \text{H}^* \text{H} = (\text{RR}^*)^{-1}. \quad (28)$$

The normal equations, augmented by the linear constraints (19), become

$$\begin{pmatrix} \text{P}^* \text{R}^* \text{H}^* \text{HRP} & \text{S}^* \\ \text{S} & \emptyset \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} \text{A} \\ \text{L} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \text{P}^* \text{R}^* \text{H}^* \text{HRD} \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (29)$$

If $\text{T}^{(3)}$ is the upper-left $(5I \ 5I)$ part of the inverse of the matrix in (29), the solution is

$$\text{A}^{(3)} = \text{T}^{(3)} \text{P}^* \text{R}^* \text{H}^* \text{HRD}, \quad (30)$$

and its covariance is

$$\text{C}_A^{(3)} = e^2 \text{T}^{(3)} \text{P}^* \text{R}^* \text{H}^* \text{HRR}^* \text{H}^* \text{HRP} \text{T}^{(3)} = \quad (31)$$

$$= e^2 \text{T}^{(3)}. \quad (32)$$

For computing $\text{P}^* \text{R}^* \text{H}^* \text{HRP}$ we notice that the j :th block of the matrix $\text{R}^* \text{H}^* \text{HR} = \text{R}^* (\text{RR}^*)^{-1} \text{R}$, of dimension $(L(j)+1|L(j)+1)$, is

$$[\text{R}^* (\text{RR}^*)^{-1} \text{R}]_j = \frac{1}{L(j)+1} \begin{pmatrix} L(j) & -1 & -1 & \dots & -1 \\ -1 & L(j) & -1 & \dots & -1 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ -1 & -1 & -1 & \dots & L(j) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (33)$$

(Note that this matrix corresponds to the operation of subtracting the scan average from each quantity belonging to that scan.) We have then

$$\text{P}^* \text{R}^* \text{H}^* \text{HRP} = \sum_{j=1}^J \text{P}_j^* [\text{R}^* (\text{RR}^*)^{-1} \text{R}]_j \text{P}_j. \quad (34)$$

3.4. Iterative solution of the rigorous equations

The matrix $P^* R^* RP$ in Solution 2, Eq. (21), has a structure very suitable for decomposition, namely by ordering the equations so that all the origin stars come last. This is however not the case for the matrix $P^* R^* (RR^*)^{-1} RP$ appearing in Solutions 3, Eq. (29). An iterative solution of (29) was outlined in a previous note [78-10-09, Eq. (20)], using $A^{(2)}$ as initial approximation, and involving only the recurrent solution of a system equivalent to (21). Let $A^{(4, n)}$ be the n :th iteration, starting with $A^{(4, 0)} = A^{(2)}$.

Eq. (29) for the solution $A^{(3)}$ can be written

$$\begin{bmatrix} P^* R^* RP & S^* \\ S & \emptyset \end{bmatrix} \times \begin{bmatrix} A \\ L \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} P^* R^* H^* HRD + (P^* R^* RP - P^* R^* H^* HRP)A \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (35)$$

from which it follows

$$A^{(3)} = T^{(2)} P^* R^* H^* HRD + T^{(2)} (P^* R^* RP - P^* R^* H^* HRP) A^{(3)}. \quad (36)$$

The first iteration is obtained by replacing $A^{(3)}$ in the right member of (36) by $A^{(2)}$. After some simplifications, the result is

$$A^{(4, 1)} = A^{(4, 0)} + T^{(2)} P^* R^* H^* H (RD - RPA^{(4, 0)}). \quad (37)$$

This formula corresponds to Eqs. (2) + (20) in the note of 78-10-09. It can obviously be iterated, and, if at all convergent, will converge to $A^{(3)}$, which according to (29) satisfies (37) as well as (36). Introducing for brevity

$$V = T^{(2)} P^* R^* H^* HR \quad \text{dimension } (5I|K) \quad (38)$$

and

$$W = I - VP, \quad \text{dimension } (5I|5I) \quad (39)$$

we have the recursion formula

$$A^{(4, n+1)} = WA^{(4, n)} + VD, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots \quad (40)$$

For the covariances of successive iterations, the recursion formulae become:

$$C^{(4, 0)} = e^2 T^{(2)} P^* R^* RR^* RPT^{(2)}, \quad (41)$$

$$F^{(4, 0)} = WN + N^* W^*; \quad (42)$$

$$C^{(4, n+1)} = WC^{(4, n)} W^* + F^{(4, n)} + M \quad (43)$$

$$F^{(4, n+1)} = WF^{(4, n)} W^* + G \quad (44)$$

where

$$M = e^2 VV^* = e^2 T^{(2)} P^* R^* H^* HRPT^{(2)} \quad \text{dimension } (5I|5I), \quad (45)$$

$$G = WM + M^*W^* \quad \text{dimension } (5I|5I), \quad (46)$$

and

$$N = e^2 \Upsilon^{(2)} \quad \text{dimension } (5I|5I). \quad (47)$$

Note that the recursions (41) - (44) involves only multiplications and additions of symmetric matrices of dimension $(5I|5I)$.

3.5. Solution using scan zero-points as unknowns

(Original three-step solution)

The abscissa corrections used as input to the observation equations in the original three-step procedure are supposed to be transformed so that the sum of the $L(j)+1$ abscissas is zero for every scan j . This is formally accomplished with the $(K|K)$ matrix $Q = R^*(RR^*)^{-1}R$ given in Eq. (33). Let Z be the $(J|1)$ array containing the unknown scan zero-point corrections, and let B be a $(K|J)$ matrix with elements

$$B_{k,j} = \delta_{j,j(k)} \quad (48)$$

(i.e. = 1 if $j(k) = j$, otherwise = 0). The observation equations are then

$$PA + BZ = QD. \quad (49)$$

The observation equation for observation k thus involves as unknowns the astrometric parameters of star $i(k)$ and the scan zero-point $Z_{j(k)}$ only. The normal equations augmented by the six linear constraints become

$$\begin{pmatrix} P^*P & S^* & P^*B \\ S & \emptyset & \emptyset \\ B^*P & \emptyset & B^*B \end{pmatrix} \times \begin{pmatrix} A \\ L \\ Z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} P^*QD \\ 0 \\ B^*QD \end{pmatrix}. \quad (50)$$

It is easily verified that $B^*Q = \emptyset$, which allows considerable simplifications.

Using the general result

$$\begin{pmatrix} a & b^* \\ b & c \end{pmatrix}^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} (a - b^*c^{-1}b)^{-1} & . \\ . & . \end{pmatrix}, \quad (50)$$

with

$$a = \begin{pmatrix} P^*P & S^* \\ S & \emptyset \end{pmatrix}, \quad b = \begin{pmatrix} B^*P & \emptyset \end{pmatrix}, \quad c = B^*B, \quad (51)$$

we find that the solution to (50) can be written

$$A^{(5)} = T^{(5)} P^* Q D, \quad (52)$$

where $T^{(5)}$ is the upper-left $(5I|5I)$ part of

$$\begin{bmatrix} P^* P - P^* B (B^* B)^{-1} B^* P & S^* \\ S & \emptyset \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (53)$$

The covariance of this solution is

$$C_A^{(5)} = e^2 T^{(5)} P^* Q Q^* P T^{(5)}. \quad (54)$$

Now it is seen that

$$Q Q^* = Q = R^* (R R^*)^{-1} R = I - B (B^* B)^{-1} B^*, \quad (55)$$

so that $P^* P - P^* B (B^* B)^{-1} B^* P = P^* R^* (R R^*)^{-1} R P$, $T^{(5)} = T^{(3)}$, $A^{(5)} = A^{(3)}$, and $C_A^{(5)} = C_A^{(3)}$. Thus:

The solution using scan zero-points as additional unknowns [Eq. (50)] is equivalent to the "rigorous" solution, using origin stars and de-correlated observation equations [Eq. (29)]. From the computational point of view, however, the solution with scan zero-points has the enormous advantage of already being of a structure suitable for a direct solution. Eq. (50) is namely a banded-bordered system of bandwidth 5 and borderwidth $J+6$, and $5I+J+6$ unknowns.

4. Scaling

The basic parameters of a numerical simulation of scans and their solution are:

- scanning law: uniform revolving scanning (asymmetric) may be assumed.
Parameters: κ (revolutions per year, formerly K) and ζ (Sun/spin-axis angle).
- number of stars: I
- number of scans: J
- number of observations: K
- duration: T (years).

These are however not independent. We shall outline how they must be related to each other in small-scale simulations.

Uniform revolving scanning means that the spin axis (z) moves with almost constant speed

$$v = 2\pi \sqrt{(1 + \kappa^2 \sin^2 \zeta)} \quad (\text{rad/yr}) \quad (56)$$

among the stars. The minimum speed guaranteeing at least six observations per year of any star is obtained for $\kappa\zeta = 270^\circ$ and is nearly independent of ζ . For $\zeta \approx 35^\circ$ it is

$$v = 28.5 \text{ rad/yr} = 1633^\circ / \text{yr} = 4.47^\circ / \text{day}. \quad (57)$$

The average density of stars, $I/4\pi$, determines the necessary field of view. It is required that on the average N stars are simultaneously in the complex field of view, which may be taken as $2w^2$ sterad, w being the width and length of each field. Thus, given N , the field size is determined by

$$w = \sqrt{(2\pi N/I)}. \quad (58)$$

The required frequency of scans, J/T , is set by the requirement that consecutive scans overlap sufficiently, e.g. by at least half the field width. Thus the minimum number of scans is

$$J = 2Tv/w. \quad (59)$$

The number of stars visible per scan, i.e. the average number of observations per scan, $L' = \langle L(j)+1 \rangle = K/J$, is the star density $I/4\pi$ times the area swept by one scan, $2\pi w$, i.e.

$$L' = wI/2. \quad (60)$$

Thus the total number of observations is

$$K = wIJ/2 = TvI. \quad (61)$$

The number of observations per star and year is independent of I and equal to $v = 28.5$.

For the baseline full-scale problem we may take $I = 10^5$ and $w = 0.9^\circ$, from which $N = 3.927$. For $T = 2$ yr we obtain the scaling parameters in Table 1.

Table 1. Basic scaling parameters for a two-year mission with on the average = 3.927 stars in the complex field of view (FOV) and 28.5 observations per star per year.

Number of stars I	Number of scans J	Number of observations K	Obs. per scan $L' = K/J$	FOV width w
100 000	7257	5 700 000	785	0.90°
30 000	3975	1 710 000	430	1.64
10 000	2295	570 000	248	2.85
3 000	1257	171 000	136	5.20
1 000	726	57 000	78.5	9.00
300	398	17 100	43.0	16.4
100	230	5 700	24.8	28.5

5. An attempted analytical solution

Notwithstanding the singularity of the submatrix $P^*P - P^*B(B^*B)^{-1}B^*P$ in Eqs. (53) and (29) we can formally obtain an approximative inverse by re-writing

$$(P^*P - P^*B(B^*B)^{-1}B^*P)^{-1} = (P^*P)^{-1} (I - P^*B(B^*B)^{-1}B^*P(P^*P)^{-1})^{-1}. \quad (62)$$

If we neglect the variation of $L(j)$ from scan to scan, i.e. assume $L(j)+1 \equiv L'$, we find that

$$P^*B(B^*B)^{-1}B^*P = \frac{1}{L'}, P^*P. \quad (63)$$

Eq. (62) then becomes simply

$$(P^*P)^{-1} (I - \frac{1}{L'}I)^{-1} = \frac{L'}{L'-1} (P^*P)^{-1}, \quad (64)$$

suggesting that the rigidity of the reconstitution is

$$r = \sqrt{(1 - \frac{1}{L'})} \quad (65)$$

which would indeed be satisfactory. Perhaps (65) or a similar formula could be rigorously proved without too much difficulty? In that case there would be little need for a numerical simulation of the reconstitution problem.